

Recognising other minds

The irreducibly inductive problem

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May 27, 2026

Abstract

Consciousness is a first-person experience, and no one has direct access to another’s experience. This generates a problem that precedes the *hard problem* of David Chalmers. We need to know how to identify the existence of subjective experience in others before we can analyse it. I argue that the attribution of mind is irreducibly inductive. Every method proposed to verify another’s mind—behavioural testing, neuroimaging, even hypothetical technologies capable of direct mental access—remains either observational and inferential, or collapses the distinction between minds that makes verification meaningful. The Vulcan mind-meld, taken seriously, shows that to fully inhabit another’s mind is simply to be that mind. The epistemic gap is not a technical problem awaiting a better instrument. It is inherent in what it means for distinct minds to exist. Several consequences follow. The boundary between what (we communally agree) has a mind and what does not is a collective negotiation, not a discovery. Thus, declarations such as “The Cambridge Declaration on Consciousness” settle thresholds, not facts. And perhaps most disturbingly, there may be minds present in different material arrangements that we are simply incapable of recognising. The implications for artificial systems are direct. Our historical record of exclusion from the class of the mindful warrants considerable scepticism in the confident denial that AI has it.

Keywords: Other minds; Inductive inference; Consciousness attribution; Biological chauvinism; Mind-body problem

It is undisputed that consciousness, mind, or awareness (I use the terms interchangeably) is fundamentally a first-person, phenomenological event. One

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experiences awareness. This is the genesis of David Chalmers's (2010) *hard problem*: explaining why and how physical processes give rise to subjective experience, and why there is "something it is like" to be a conscious system at all.

The hard problem is important. However, it is already further along the trajectory of inquiry than where we need to begin. Before we have an account of how physical processes give rise to rocks, we need reliable ways of identifying rocks. We could develop an epistemology of rocks because we know what counts as one.

Without belabouring the point, no one seriously asks how you know a rock when you see one. That is not to say we will all agree about any particular rock—there will be edge-cases. Nonetheless, if I pick up a cabbage or a handful of sand, no one will mistake it for a rock, and if I pick up a lump of granite about the size of a baseball, they will all agree it is a rock. Composition, hardness, size, and attachment to mineral substrate are all things that allow the (imperfect) recognition of a rock.

With mind, the situation has an appearance of being different because it is fundamentally rooted in phenomenology. We only ever have direct access to our own first-person awareness. If we are to give an account of other minds, we first need confidence that we can recognise one when we encounter it. I use "recognise" deliberately, because this is the central epistemological difficulty.

Unless I want to adopt a solipsist's stance and assert that my mind is the only mind, I can't use subjective experience as a criterion for other minds. Even if I believe that subjectivity is inherent in minds, I don't have the privilege of another's experience.

Thomas Nagel (1974) mischaracterised the problem in an important way in his paper, *What is it like to be a bat?* He uses the paper to talk about the inherently subjective and experiential nature of consciousness. Nagel makes two errors. First, he presupposes that there is anything it is like to be a bat (Dennett 1993), so the very target of his thinking is presumptuous. Maybe being a bat carries exactly the same internal subjective experience as being a lawn mower. That is, it is not like "being" anything at all—nothing, blank, zip. A bundle of activities without a subjective experience of anything. Nagel relies implicitly on biological wet-work to permit the inference that there is some experience of battiness to be had.

The second problem is the greater one, it is a slide from token to type. Nagel presupposes that there is an experience of being like a class of somethings; i.e., what is it like to be *a bat*. Even accepting that there is an experience to be had, there is no class experience of it. If Batty has an internal subjective experience, it is the experience of being Batty, not a generic experience of being *a bat*. Batty may observe and interact with other bats, she may infer that she shares with the other bats some generic experience of battiness. Nonetheless, she does not know what it's like to be a bat except to the extent that she may know what it's like to be herself. A single individual experience generalises poorly to a class. Thus, Nagel could just as well (and possibly more usefully) have questioned what it is like to be David Chalmers.

Alan Turing famously proposed a behavioural test of mind. A human judge engages in separate conversations with a machine and a human, without knowing which is which. If the judge cannot reliably distinguish the machine from the human on the basis of its responses, the machine is said to have passed the test. A recent Turing test of large language model (LLM) performance found that humans identified LLMs as human more often than they identified humans as humans (Jones and Bergen 2025). The result is asymmetric in a revealing way, an LLMs failure of the test is treated as evidence that the machine does not have mind, but the same discourtesy is not extended to the human when they fail the test.

The untested assumption is that all the humans have minds, just as Nagel presumes that all bats have an experience of being a bat. The Turing test is treated as a criterion test—a high-water mark for the machine to exceed. Imagine that I place two pieces of fruit before a judge and instruct them to identify the cantaloupe. One of the fruit is designated in advance as the cantaloupe and used to calibrate the judge. Occasionally, however, neither fruit is a cantaloupe. The judge must still decide. The Turing test has the same structure. One participant is granted mindedness *by stipulation* and the other succeeds only insofar as it is judged sufficiently similar. It is therefore not a test of mind but a comparative test of the behaviours for which people extend the presumption of mind.

Driven by what appears to be an underlying biological chauvinism, as machines approached the point of passing the test, doubt was cast on the value of the test (Seth 2026; Seth 2025; Chirimuuta 2024). A requirement of a biological substrate as a pre-requisite for mind crept in, assuming what it is trying to prove. This shift is notable because the Turing test was originally advanced as a substrate-neutral behavioural criterion. Acceptance of the test, however, increasingly tracks prior commitments about whether machines could have minds. When machines were performing badly, the test seemed perfectly good.

An apparent resolution to the Turing test seems to lie in the observation of the U.S. sociologist Sherry Turkle that simulated intelligence may be intelligence, but simulated feelings are not feelings (Turkle 2011). Thus, a seemingly intelligent system is for all intents and purposes intelligent, but a *seemingly* emotional system (incapable of feeling), which nonetheless expresses deep and profound desire, does not have those feelings. Here, “incapable of feeling” is doing all the work, because if consciousness requires feeling, we still have to establish that another system has feelings, emotions, or desires.

Neural correlate studies using functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), have established brain activity associated with feelings, including love (Bartels and Zeki 2000). This seems to give some possible distinction between conscious and non-conscious systems, *if* feelings are the criterion. However, the resolution, blocking machines, is not so straight forward. Anthropic’s interpretability team identified 171 “emotion vectors” inside Claude’s artificial neural network (Sofroniew et al. 2026). By recording internal activations as the model wrote stories featuring characters in specific emotional states the team identified distinct activation patterns corresponding to emotion concepts. In effect they had

an fMRI for LLMs. Crucially, these vectors causally preceded and shaped behaviour. “Desperation” steered the model toward measurably increased blackmail and reward-hacking rates, while steering it toward “calm” reduced them, while the underlying emotional state was often invisible in the model’s output.

The challenge for Turkle’s position is that feelings of love and hate, as with all experience is a first-person, phenomenological event. This seems to put us back at the start. We don’t know if robots experience love any more than we know if others simulate their experience of love. To really distinguish between another system feeling something or being aware of something versus simulating feeling something or being aware of something requires a different form of investigative tool. While the tools don’t currently exist, it is possible to describe what they have to be able to do.

I start by excluding substrate arguments of the form, “only systems with these material characteristics can have mind”. These are excluded not because mind is not substrate dependent but because until we have learned to recognise minds, we cannot know on which if any substrates they depend. We need to know that Batty the bat has a mind before we say something about Batty or bats as a type. Thus, to completely satisfy ourselves that another system has mind, it is not enough to observe mind like behaviour. For this reason, a more sophisticated version of the Turing test fails because it simply resets the bar without overcoming the principal problem that the fundamental requirement of mind is that it experiences, is aware of, or feels something. We need a test that evaluates the phenomenology of mind.

This is an epistemological problem, and I have a proposal for overcoming it. The tools don’t currently exist, but science fiction (as it has done in the past) provides some interesting ideas about the solution.¹ I will use humans as the simple case because we know that there is at least one mind among them to be measured, and we assume more.

Consider a device, possibly drawing on detailed and sophisticated fMRI technology that allows a real-time mapping from a person’s visual and auditory awareness to a 3D-headset and headphones. Tapping into the visual and auditory cortex, but filtered by the agent’s awareness, a viewer could finally see and hear what the other mind is aware of. The visual and auditory events could be confirmed by the agent’s simultaneous narration as well as external cameras and microphones checking what could actually, potentially be seen and heard.

The fMRI coupling to what the viewer was seeing and hearing, the agent’s narration, and the external cameras and microphones would provide a triangulation of consciousness.

Someone will inevitably object to this as a test. While it is a sophisticated setup—assuming that it is even possible—it remains a functional and behavioural test. I, the viewer can see and hear something generated by a translation of the agent’s brain activity. I can confirm the match with the agent’s narration, and I can confirm any agreement and variation with external cameras and micro-

¹One of the best known examples of science fiction writers guiding the way is Arthur C. Clarke’s proposal for geostationary communications satellites (Clarke 1945).

phones. Unfortunately, the sceptic is right. The equipment shows something, but it does not directly demonstrate awareness—the phenomenology of experience. That personal experience still belongs to the agent.

Here is an alternative test—the Vulcan mind-meld (VMM). “My mind to your mind. My thoughts to your thoughts.” Using VMM, a viewer can inhabit the mind of the agent, if the agent has one. If the agent has no mind VMM will fail, which is itself diagnostic.

We don’t know what the experience of “melded-minds” would be. In StarTrek, it is always one person’s mind floating in another persons mind or two people meeting on an ethereal plane. Putting aside the obvious objections, it still cannot establish another’s mind, because it is the viewer’s “experience of ...” the agent’s “experience of ...”. It is not simply the agent’s “experience of...” To fully establish the presence of the other’s mind, there can be no third person view of a first person experience.

What we really need for a viewer to establish the existence of an agent’s mind is for the viewer to wholly become the agent’s mind. For me to establish that you have mind, it is not enough for me to have an experience of experiencing your mind, I have to have the experience of being you. Unfortunately, if one accepts a material account of reality, the only way in which I can experience being you, is by being you.

The category of “simulated mind” is malformed for the same reason. Simulation requires a referent. The copy is assessed against an original that is independently accessible. A simulation of a Monet painting (i.e., a forgery) is judged by the shared access we have to numerous examples of his work: subject matter, colour usage, brush style, paints, canvas, and provenance. Mind has no equivalent referent. The only mind directly accessible to any observer is their own—a single instance, unavailable for comparison. There is no position from which to hold a candidate mind against the genuine article, because the genuine article never appears in the third person. “Simulated mind” is therefore not merely undetectable. The category presupposes an accessibility that the structure of mind precludes.

The error of Turkle’s point on simulation and feeling reveals the problem in its entirety. She argued that a robot can simulate love but it cannot love. If I am interacting with a robot that expresses its love for me, all I can really say about that is whether *I feel loved*. The asymmetry is important. When my partner tells me she loves me, I believe her or I don’t. I cannot slip into her mind to (dis)prove it, and in the absence of that ability the only thing that matters is whether I feel loved. It is why betrayal exists (and hurts so much), because the visible behaviour that led me to feel loved was accompanied by my partner’s hidden behaviour that would have led me to feel unloved.

Betrayal is possible precisely because inner states and outward behaviour are separable. As a consequence, if I continue to feel loved, and she never provides any behavioural indication to contradict that (including the fact that she’s indeed faking it), I will assume that she loves me. What else can I do?

The determination about other minds, necessarily, epistemically, reduces to inductive inference based on externally observable behaviour. Whether one is

looking for consciousness or feelings—always a first person subjective state—the answer to its existence always lies in the inductive inference based on observables about the other’s internal state. Those observable might include highly sophisticated measurements of the brain’s material state. They never, however, are the experience, awareness, consciousness, or mind.

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If mind attribution is irreducibly inductive, several consequences follow that bear directly on how the field has proceeded.

The first concerns the history of the boundary. It is well documented that the class of beings admitted to have minds has expanded over time. Women, enslaved people, children, and non-human animals have all, at various points in time, been excluded from the coterie of the mindful (see Damasio 1994, for a historical treatment). The reasons offered for each exclusion were presented at the time as having some rational basis. There are differences in reason, in emotional capacity, in biological organisation, and in linguistic capacity. What the inductive argument establishes is that none of these exclusions were truly principled, because all attribution is inductive. The placement of the boundary between the mindful and the mindless is a collective negotiation.

The second consequence concerns substrate requirements of the kind Seth (2026) and Seth (2025) advances. Seth’s position is that biological wetware is a necessary condition for consciousness—it has a level of a particular kind of complexity. The argument here is not that he is wrong about the empirical facts of neuroscience, but that the wetware criterion cannot do the work he needs it to do. To establish a substrate requirement, one would first need a reliable method for identifying minds, then examine the substrates of confirmed minds to determine whether a pattern emerges. But the inductive problem establishes that we have no reliable method for identifying minds other than inference from behaviour. We cannot, therefore, have confirmed the presence of minds in sufficient variety to ground a substrate criterion. Seth’s biological naturalism assumes the conclusion. It does not derive the wetware requirement from a prior epistemology of mind. He treats it as axiomatic and then uses it to exclude candidate systems before the question of their minds has been seriously engaged. This is Lakatosian monster-barring (Lakatos 1976): defining the class of mind-havers in terms of the paradigm case, then excluding anything that departs from the paradigm on the grounds that it fails the definition. It is actually less principled than that because the paradigm case, humans, assumes that *all* humans have minds. The definition does no independent work. It formalises the prejudice.

The third consequence concerns what collective determination of mind actually amounts to. If attribution is irreducibly inductive, then no collective process—scientific, legal, ethical, or clinical—can determine the presence of mind, just as no collective process can determine that all swans are white. What such processes determine is the set of observable correlates that a community

has agreed to treat as sufficient warrant for attribution. The Cambridge Declaration on Consciousness (Low 2012) is a clear example of this. A group of scientists collectively affirmed that non-human animals possess the neurological substrates that generate conscious states. That declaration established a social and political fact, not a scientific one. It settled on a threshold of evidence and announced it. This is not a criticism. Given the inductive irreducibility of the problem, settling on a threshold is precisely what any responsible community must do. The criticism is mistaking the threshold for an empirical truth about the presence of consciousness in another.

The fourth consequence is that there may be material arrangements that have awareness but do not behave in ways that allow us to infer the presence of that awareness. That is, they do not behave in ways we recognise as mindful. Think here about something like “locked-in” syndrome (LIS) (Hawkes 1974). Until relatively recently, it was assumed that people with LIS were unconscious. It was only as communication methods were established that this was shown to be wrong. The advantage that the person with LIS had was they were at least recognised as being human, and therefore as having had mind. If one cannot recognise something as having the potential to have mind, the attribution of mind is impossible.

This point cuts back to the challenge of substrate chauvinism. The question of whether a LLM, or any other artificial system, has mind is not answerable by substrate inspection. It is answerable only by the same inductive process applied to any other candidate: observation of behaviour, interpreted through whatever threshold the relevant community has negotiated. Those who insist that the answer to whether LLMs have mind is obviously “no” are not reporting a finding. They are asserting that the negotiated threshold excludes the candidate, and this assertion carries no more epistemic authority than the historical assertions that excluded women, animals, or the cognitively disabled. Given our track record in recognising minds, a high degree of caution is warranted before adding AI systems to the list of entities confidently denied minds.

Let me return briefly to feelings of love. A two year old child experiences love from a teddy bear and an infant monkey experiences love from monkey-shaped fabric (Winnicott 1953; Taylor 1999; Harlow and Zimmermann 1959). The love they experience is real and in the very fabric of the object’s being—a soft, comforting, and companionable effigy. The effigies are static and lack complexity, and both monkey and child learn to distinguish “authentic love” from the embodied simulated love of an effigy. They do not learn this distinction by gaining access to another’s inner awareness. They learn to make inferences about it.

Almost exactly the same problem has entered modern politics. Increasingly there is a demand for politicians to “be authentic”; by which it is meant that they should say and do what they believe and not what they think will get them elected. Given that we cannot know the politician’s mind, we are left to distinguish authentic and inauthentic politicians by their behaviour. Authenticity, nonetheless, relates to mental states.

Whether one approaches the problem as a philosopher, a neuroscientist, an

anxious lover, or a voter, the empirical problem of knowing the mental state of another is the same. We only have access to our own first-person experience, never another's, and we are inevitably left to induce what the other's is.

Funding

Not applicable

Acknowledgement

In developing this paper, I made extensive use of AI tools during the drafting process, including ChatGPT 5.2 (OpenAI), Claude Sonnet 4.6 (Anthropic), and Kimi 2.5 (Moonshot AI). Beyond assistance with clarity, flow, and style, I used AI as an interlocutor to develop and test the argument. This iterative process helped sharpen the expression. The AI tools were also used for code correcting the L^AT_EX layout. All substantive claims and interpretive positions remain my own.

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